

Adsorption of Phosphate by Ferric Oxide Systems

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The adsorption characteristics of phosphate on ferric oxide systems have been investigated. For this study, iron oxide has been prepared in four physicochemically different forms, namely, sol, gel, ignited and crystalline. The adsorption isotherms at various pH values obtained in the usual way conform more or less with that of Freundlich. It was not a clear case of exchange of phosphate for OH^- ions but could be partly so.

The majority of experiments on anion adsorption by soils and clays is restricted to phosphate interaction. This is partly due to the fact that phosphate is extremely important as a plant nutrient and partly due to its complex nature. As a result of the latter, contradictory observations have often been reported.

Kurtz, De-Turk and Bray¹ regarded phosphate adsorption as anion exchange. In fact, the nature and extent of anion exchange, particularly with phosphate depends markedly on the type of the material concerned. An evaluation in this direction is especially important when the exchange substance is a soil. A soil may consist of one or more of the clay minerals, small quantities of salts, organic matter and iron and aluminium oxides. The sesquioxides of iron and aluminium may be present in a wide variety of forms, all of which are more or less active in so far as phosphate adsorption is concerned.

The rapid adsorption of soluble phosphates by the hydrated iron and aluminium oxides has been reported by Ford², Heck³, Romine and Metzger⁴, Coleman^{5a,5b} and Barbier *et al.*⁶. According to them, most soils, particularly the lateritic soils and the B-horizons of podzolic soils, contain considerable amounts of these oxides as coatings on soil particles, and the colloidal nature of these oxides renders them active for phosphate adsorption.

It is interesting to note that Stelly and Pierre⁷ found in their experiments that the iron phosphate minerals dufrenite [$\text{FePO}_4 \cdot \text{Fe}(\text{OH})_3$] and vivianite [$\text{Fe}_3(\text{PO}_4)_2 \cdot 8\text{H}_2\text{O}$] showed solubility in the pH range 3.0-6.0 and 6.0-7.0 respectively, while aluminium phosphate

1. T. Kurtz, E. E. De-Turk and R. H. Bray, *Soil Sci.*, 1946, **61**, 111.
2. M. C. Ford, *J. Amer. Soc. Agron.*, 1933, **25**, 134.
3. A. F. Heck, *Soil Sci.*, 1934, **37**, 343.
4. D. S. Romine and W. H. Metzger, *J. Amer. Soc. Agron.*, 1939, **31**, 99.
- 5a. R. Coleman, *Proc. Soil Sci. Soc. Amer.*, 1942, **7**, 134.
- 5b. Idem. *Proc. Soil. Sci. Soc. Amer.*, 1944, **9**, 72.
- 5c. Idem. *Soil Sci.*, 1944, **58**, 71.
6. G. Barbier *et al.*, *Plant and Soil.*, 1948, **1**, 11.
7. M. Stelly and W. H. Pierre, *Proc. Soil Sci. Soc. Amer.*, 1942, **7**, 39.

minerals like variscite [$\text{AlPO}_4 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$] and wavellite [$\text{Al}_3(\text{OH})_3 \cdot (\text{PO}_2)_3 \cdot 5\text{H}_2\text{O}$] showed the same behaviour in the range 4.5–7.0. Coleman^{5c} observed that most of the phosphate adsorption took place at $p\text{H}$ 3.0, but when the free iron oxides were removed from the soil, the adsorption came down to more or less the same value at $p\text{H}$ 3.0, 7.0 and 9.5. Heck³ concluded that the $p\text{H}$ of the soil greatly influences the chemical forms of adsorbed phosphate.

Ford² showed that only hydrated iron oxides can adsorb phosphate. Kelly and Midgley⁸ observed an increase in $p\text{H}$ on mixing ferric hydroxide and phosphate solution at the same $p\text{H}$ and thereby suggested a physicochemical anion exchange equilibrium in which phosphate ions replaced the exposed OH^- ions from the colloidal hydrated sesquioxides.

Thus if iron oxide, fresh, aged or crystalline, adsorbs phosphate solely by exchange with OH^- ions on the surface, there should be a quantitative relationship between the phosphate adsorbed and the OH^- ions released. It is, however, not unlikely that phosphate may react chemically with iron on the surface in an irreversible manner.

EXPERIMENTAL

Preparation of iron oxide in the sol, gel, ignited and crystalline conditions.

Iron oxide sol : The procedure was the same as that of the preparation of Graham's sol with slight modification. To a solution of FeCl_3 (10%) a saturated solution of $(\text{NH}_4)_2\text{CO}_3$ was added until a permanent precipitate was obtained. The precipitate formed was washed repeatedly with boiling water until the washed liquid was free from chloride. It was then peptized by adding a few drops of 2% FeCl_3 solution and purified by dialysis against distilled water for 4 days. The sol having a colloid content 2.1 g/litre was stored in a stoppered Jena glass bottle.

Iron oxide gel : A sample of the sol prepared above was dried over a hot plate maintained at about 80° .

Ignited iron Oxide : A sample of the sol was dried in a Pt-basin and heated strongly over a Meker burner for 12 hours.

Crystalline iron oxide : Natural haematite was ground and minus 100 mesh sieved material was used for the present experiments.

The phosphorus content was determined by the vanado-molybdophosphoric acid method in nitric acid⁹. The colour developed was matched in an E.E.L. photoelectric colorimeter after allowing 20 min. against a blank, using 1 or 4 cm. cell and Filter No. 602. Standard curves were obtained under identical conditions.

For the purpose of each experiment with the sol 25 ml of it was taken and made up with phosphate buffer and water to 100 ml. The amount of phosphate adsorbed was determined after allowing 7 days for reaction. In the case of the solid oxides, the initial concentrations and $p\text{H}$ of the phosphate buffer solutions corresponded with having the same colloid

8. J. B. Kelley and A. R. Midgley, *Soil Sci.*, 1943, 55, 167.

9. M. L. Jackson. *Soil Chemical Analysis*, 1958. Constable and Co. Ltd., London.

content. The results of adsorption and pH changes are given below in Tables 1A, 1B, 1C and 1D.

It is evident from the results given in the tables that adsorption increases with increased concentration of phosphate following more or less the Freundlich isotherm (Fig. 1).

Adsorption in the acidic range is somewhat greater than that in the alkaline range. Ferric oxide in the sol form shows maximum adsorption, while minimum adsorption is observed in case of ignited oxide.

TABLE 1A (Sol)

Initial P-concn. (g/lit)	Initial pH	Eqm. P-concn. g/lit).	Eqm.pH	P-adsorbed (g/g)	OH ions released (g-ions/lit) $\times 10^9$
0.1	5.15	0.07	5.31	0.07	0.63
0.3	4.90	0.22	5.29	0.17	1.15
0.6	4.76	0.42	5.34	0.27	1.61
0.9	4.72	0.73	5.42	0.34	2.10
1.2	4.67	0.99	5.52	0.41	2.84
					$\times 10^9$
0.1	8.16	0.07	8.37	0.07	0.89
0.3	8.44	0.23	8.77	0.13	3.13
0.6	8.62	0.48	9.02	0.24	6.30
0.9	8.67	0.74	9.12	0.30	8.50
1.2	8.82	1.03	9.27	0.33	12.01

TABLE 1B (Gel)

Eqm.P (g/lit)	Eqm.pH	P-adsorbed (g/g)	OH ions released (g-ions/lit) $\times 10^9$
0.08	5.25	0.05	0.37
0.22	5.14	0.16	0.60
0.47	5.22	0.26	1.08
0.75	5.31	0.31	1.52
1.02	5.31	0.37	1.56
			$\times 10^9$
0.08	8.24	0.04	0.27
0.23	8.64	0.14	1.61
0.49	9.00	0.23	5.83
0.76	9.09	0.28	7.62
1.04	9.27	0.33	12.01

TABLE 1C (Ignited Oxide)

0.10	5.15	0	—
0.28	4.92	0.05	—
0.56	4.78	0.09	—
0.85	4.75	0.11	—
1.13	4.69	0.13	—
0.10	8.17	0	—
0.28	8.44	0.05	—
0.56	8.65	0.09	—
0.85	8.69	0.11	—
1.15	8.82	0.10	—

TABLE 1D (Crystalline Oxide)

Eqm. <i>P</i> (g/lit)	Eqm. <i>pH</i>	<i>P</i> -adsorbed (g/g)	OH ions released (g-ions/lit) $\times 10^9$
0.10	5.15	0	—
0.26	4.92	0.09	—
0.52	4.96	0.16	0.34
0.79	5.00	0.21	0.48
1.08	5.06	0.24	0.68
			$\times 10^6$
0.10	8.18	0	—
0.28	8.48	0.05	0.26
0.55	8.78	0.11	1.86
0.83	8.90	0.14	3.27
1.13	9.16	0.15	7.84

Fig 1. Adsorption of phosphate on different Ferric Oxide Systems.

DISCUSSION

The relative proportions of H_2PO_4 ions in the buffer range of phosphate solutions used are much higher and it is assumed that this species alone takes part in a possible exchange reaction with OH ions present as counter ions in the positively charged ferric oxide sol, gel and haematite (adsorption was very small with ignited oxide and hence OH ions released by H_2PO_4 ions could not be calculated). A linear relationship (graph not shown) between the amounts of absorbed phosphate and OH ions released (vide Tables IA to 1D) may suggest

a similar view. But if the actual amounts of the respective ions are compared, the fact emerges that H_2PO_4 ions are adsorbed in far greater quantity (10^6 and 10^3 times in the acidic and alkaline ranges respectively) than OH ions. Consequently, a very large part of the exchange appears to be nonionic, in the sense that no corresponding anion is exchanged for the phosphate adsorbed. The nonionic adsorption may be physical and/or chemical in nature.

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